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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION - INGREDIENTS OF *PANCHATIKTA CHURNA*

1. Jyoti Bhagiya, Second year P.G. Scholar, Upgraded P.G. Department of *Dravyaguna*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India
2. Dharmendra Jani, Associate Professor, Upgraded P.G. Department of *Dravyaguna*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India
3. Isha Adhyaru, Lab Technician, Upgraded P.G. Department of *Dravyaguna*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

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Abstract

Background: The quality and efficacy of compound formulations depend largely on the quality of raw material used. Our plant-based drug industry too needs quality parameters for medicinal plants for the production of quality ensured standardized herbal drugs. Powder microscopy is a part of pharmacognosy that helps to identify and authenticate the drugs as well as impurities. *Panchatikta* is a reputed poly-herbal formulation of Ayurveda. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Panchatikta* was carried out. *Panchatikta* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Hook.f. and Thoms), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss), *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.), *Kantakari* (*Solanum virginianum* L.) and *Patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.). Slides of each ingredient of *Panchatikta* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Panchatikta* shows starch grains, fragment of fibers, trichome, pitted vessel, stone cells etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Panchatikta* helps in correct identification of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Hook.f. and Thoms), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss), *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.), *Kantakari* (*Solanum virginianum* L.) and *Patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.). thus,

For Corresponds:

Name of Author: Dr. Jyoti Bhagiya

Email:

jyotibhagiya18598@gmail.com

Key Words:

Powder microscopy, *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Hook.f. and Thoms), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss), *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.), *Kantakari* (*Solanum virginianum* L.), *Patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.)

INTRODUCTION

In our country nearly 7500 plant species are being used in the formulation of medicinal plant-based health care products. The quality and efficacy of these preparations depend largely on the quality of raw material used. The increase in the reported incidence of toxicity, indiscriminate use and easy availability of herbal preparations and food supplements makes it imperative to lay down standards which could ensure their quality, safety and efficacy. Our plant-based drug industry too needs quality parameters for medicinal plants for the production of quality ensured standardized herbal drugs. Evolving methods of standardization and establishing quality control parameters for herbal drugs calls for a well-planned approach for establishing standards and this can be achieved only through systematic evaluation of the plant material using modern analytical techniques.

Powder microscopy is a part of pharmacognosy that helps to identify and authenticate the drugs as well as impurities. Here, for the present study *Panchatikta* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Panchatikta* is a reputed poly-herbal formulation of Ayurveda¹. It contains *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Hook.f. and Thoms), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss), *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.), *Kantakari* (*Solanum virginianum* L.) and *Patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.)

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Panchatikta*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features such as starch grains, fragment of fibres, trichome, pitted vessel, stone cells etc. in the powder of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Hook.f. and Thoms), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss), *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.), *Kantakari* (*Solanum virginianum* L.) and *Patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.)
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Panchatikta was used for the powder microscopy. *Panchatikta* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Hook.f. and Thoms), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss), *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.), *Kantakari* (*Solanum virginianum* L.) and *Patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.). Stem of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Hook.f. Thoms), Bark of *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss), Leaves of *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.), Root of *Kantakari* (*Solanum virginianum* L.) and Leaves of *Patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.) were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Panchatikta* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.²⁻⁶

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No. 1: Powder microscopic characters found in *Panchatikta Churna*

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Vasa</i>	<i>Kantakari</i>	<i>Patol</i>
1.	Starch grains	+	+		+	

2.	Vessel element	+				
3.	Prism	+				
4.	Crystal fibre	+				
5.	Fibre	+		+	+	+
6.	Tracheids	+				
7.	Fragments of fibres		+			
8.	Fragments of tannin		+			
9.	Fragments of cork with stone cells		+			
10.	Crystals of calcium oxalate		+			
11.	Fragments of fibres associated with crystals		+			
12.	Cystolith			+		
13.	Fragment of transversely cut piece of lamina			+		
14.	Trichome			+		+
15.	Spiral vessels			+		
16.	Fragment of stellate trichome				+	
17.	Pitted vessel				+	
18.	Sclerides from spines				+	
19.	Pollen grain				+	
20.	Transversely cut testa				+	
21.	Cells of epicarp					+
22.	Stone cells					+
23.	Resin duct					+

Table No. 2: Powder microscopic study of *Guduchi*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Guduchi</i>	Figure no.
1.	Starch grains	[Fig. 1.a]
2.	Vessel element	[Fig. 1.b]

3.	Prism	[Fig. 1.c]
4.	Crystal fibre	[Fig. 1.c]
5.	Fibre	[Fig. 1.d]
6.	Tracheids	[Fig. 1.e]

Table No. 3: Powder microscopic study of *Nimba*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Nimba</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fragments of fibres	[Fig. 2.a]
2.	Fragments of tannin	[Fig. 2.b]
3.	Fragments of cork with stone cells	[Fig. 2.c]
4.	Crystals of calcium oxalate	[Fig. 2.d]
5.	Starch grains	[Fig. 2.e]
6.	Fragments of fibres associated with crystals	[Fig. 2.f]

Table No. 4: Powder microscopic study of *Vasa*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Vasa</i>	Figure no.
1.	Cystolith	[Fig. 3.a]
2.	Fragment of transversely cut piece of lamina	[Fig. 3.b]
3.	Trichome	[Fig. 3.c]
4.	Spiral vessels	[Fig. 3.d]
5.	Fibre	[Fig. 3.e]

Table No. 5: Powder microscopic study of *Kantakari*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Kantakari</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fiber	[Fig. 4.a]
2.	Fragment of stellate trichome	[Fig. 4.b]
3.	Pitted vessel	[Fig. 4.c]
4.	Sclerides from spines	[Fig. 4.d]
5.	Pollen grain	[Fig. 4.e]

6.	Starch grain	[Fig. 4.e]
7.	Transversely cut testa	[Fig. 4.f]

Table No. 6: Powder microscopic study of *Patol*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Patol</i>	Figure no.
1.	Cells of epicarp	[Fig. 5.a]
2.	Simple trichome	[Fig. 5.b]
3.	Stone cells	[Fig. 5.c]
4.	Fibre	[Fig. 5.d]
5.	Resin duct	[Fig. 5.e]

Through this present study information regarding the microscopic characters of the herbal drug can be known. For this microscopic study, powder of *Panchatikta* was selected. The microscopic characters of *Panchatikta* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Guduchi* shows, starch grains, vessel element, prism, crystal fibre, fibre and tracheids. Powder microscopy of *Nimba* shows, fragments of fibres, fragments of tannin, fragments of cork with stone cells, crystals of calcium oxalate, starch grains and fragments of fibres associated with crystals. Powder microscopy of *Vasa* shows, cystolith, fragment of transversely cut piece of lamina, trichome, spiral vessels and fibre. Powder microscopy of *Kantakari* shows, fiber, fragment of stellate trichome, pitted vessel, sclerides from spines, pollen grain, starch grain and transversely cut testa. Powder microscopy of *Patol* shows, cells of epicarp, simple trichome, stone cells, fibre and resin duct.

Plate No. 1: Photos of powder microscopic study of *Guduchi*

[Fig. 1.a]

Starch grains

[Fig. 1.b]

Vessel element

[Fig. 1.c]

Prism
Crystal fibre

[Fig. 1.d]

Fibre

[Fig. 1.e]

Tracheids

Plate No. 2: Photos of powder microscopic study of *Nimba*

Fragments of fibres

[Fig. 2.a]

Fragments of tannin

[Fig. 2.b]

s

Fragments of cork with stone cells

[Fig. 2.c]

Crystals of calcium oxalate

[Fig. 2.d]

Starch grains

[Fig. 2.e]

Fragments of fibres associated with crystals

[Fig. 2.f]

Plate No. 3: Photos of powder microscopic study of *Vasa*

Cystolith

[Fig. 3.a]

Fragment of transversely cut piece of lamina

[Fig. 3.b]

Trichome

[Fig. 3.c]

Spiral vessels

[Fig. 3.d]

Fibre

[Fig. 3.e]

Plate No. 4: Photos of powder microscopic study of *Kantakari*

Fiber

[Fig. 4.a]

Fragment of stellate trichome

[Fig. 4.b]

Pitted vessel

[Fig. 4.c]

Sclerides from spines

[Fig. 4.d]

Pollen grain
Starch grain

[Fig. 4.e]

Transversely cut testa

[Fig. 4.f]

Plate No. 5: Photos of powder microscopic study of *Patol*

[Fig. 5.a]

Cells of
epicarp

[Fig. 5.b]

Simple trichome

[Fig. 5.c]

Stone cells

[Fig. 5.d]

Fibre

[Fig. 5.e]

Resin duct

CONCLUSION:

The current study's finding aid in the identification of *Panchatikta*. According to observations, microscopic characters such as starch grains, vessel elements, prism, crystal fibre, fibre and tracheids indicates the presence of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Hook.f. and Thoms). Microscopic characters such as fragments of fibres, fragments of tannin, fragments of cork with stone cells, crystals of calcium oxalate, starch grains and fragments of fibres associated with crystals indicates the presence of *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss). Microscopic characters such as cystolith, fragment of transversely cut piece of lamina, trichome, spiral vessels and fibre indicates the presence of *Vasa* (*Adhatoda vasica* Nees.). Microscopic characters such as fiber, fragment of stellate trichome, pitted vessel, sclerides from spines, pollen grain, starch grain and transversely cut testa indicates the presence of *Kantakari* (*Solanum virginianum* L.). Microscopic characters such as cells of epicarp, simple trichome, stone cells, fibre and resin duct indicates the presence of *Patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.). In order to improve public health, herbal medicine must be subjected to powder microscopy before being released into the pharmaceutical market.

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